

Speculation on Fermi's Golden Rule

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We have argued in previous notes that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is a modulus 1 (representing a uniform distribution under reduced information) complex probability. It represents the spatial probability for hits in space by the inherent force. Given that this complex probability may interfere, it has an effect on average kinetic energy: $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W/W$ where $W = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. One has various free particle interaction probabilities as the particle is interacting with a potential. Both the numerator and denominator of the average kinetic energy are related to the interaction spatial density, but by dividing the two one obtains the classical kinetic energy. Thus, the classical picture is present alongside the quantum one.

The interference of $\exp(ipx)$ s in a time independent problem can give rise to interaction points with zero or very low probability. This, however, does not mean that the velocity is 0 at these points. For example, a particle in an infinite well has $KE_{ave}(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \sin(pave x) / \sin(pave x) = pave pave/2m$. This result matches $x=v_{rms} t$ which is the motion of the particle because it is not interacting with a potential. Nevertheless, the interaction spatial density is $W^*W = C \sin(pave x) \sin(pave x)$. We have argued that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is a probability which conserves energy and momentum in a two body elastic collision. Energy conservation should hold for a 1-dimensional single particle bound state as one creates an energy resonance when creating a bound state. This is important because we argue that transitions from one energy level to another should be linked with energy considerations, in particular $\langle W_1 V W_2 \rangle$. We first note that the Schrodinger equation, which is a conservation of nonrelativistic energy, establishes an energy resonance. $V(x)$ is the classical energy which may be considered to be a number at x , one has E on the RHS of the equation and average kinetic energy: $\{-1/2m \sum_p a(p) p^2 \exp(ipx)\} / \{\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)\}$ on the LHS. Thus, it requires two pieces of information $\{-1/2m \sum_p a(p) p^2 \exp(ipx)\}$ and $V(x)W(x)$ to determine if one has a resonance energy state. In principle, if one only had $V(x)W(x)$, this is a math function which may be written as $\sum_i a_n W_n(x)$, where n is the energy level. We argue that given $V(x)W(x)$, one should first calculate $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ to see if one has an energy resonance, because this is a steady solution (if no V perturbation exists). Otherwise, $V(x)W(x)$ may be seen as a sum of states $\sum_n a_n W_n(x)$ and should not depend on the energy of $W(x)$. Given that $V(x)W(x)$ represents an interaction between $W(x)$ and $V(x)$, $\sum_n a_n W_n(x)$ represents the weighted bound state amplitudes and $\langle W_1 V(x) W_2 \rangle * \langle W_2 V(x) W_1 \rangle$ should be proportional to the transition probability and not depend on any energy of W_1 or W_2 . One may create units of probability/per sec by dividing by $1/\hbar$ and multiplying by density(E) which has units of $1/E$. Thus, we argue that it is the single particle bound state resonance based on conservation of energy which gives rise to Fermi's Golden rule. We note that (1) derives Fermi's Golden Rule in a somewhat different manner.

We suggest that $-Et+px$, a Lorentz invariant, is akin to a potential for a particle with rest mass and so $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is linked with a potential. This also holds for an electrostatic potential, while a photon has $\cos(-Et+px)$ apply directly to the inherent force and not a potential. A single particle Schrodinger equation, however, deals with a particle with rest mass m_0 and so it is the potential energy which is the key idea for quantum interactions. We suggest that quantum

mechanics is inherently a potential based theory (with the exception of the photon) and this is why Fermi's Golden Rule is based on $\langle W_1 | V | W_2 \rangle$. In other words, in quantum mechanics, force follows from a potential and not the other way around as in Newtonian mechanics. In quantum mechanics, the rest mass of a particle represents an inherent force which is linked with a probabilistic hit pattern in space given by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. Thus, the inherent force gives rise to a probabilistic potential which in turn gives rise to a term proportional to force $-\text{grad}(-iEt+ipx) = p$. This seems to explain why quantum mechanics equations deal with potential instead of force. The probabilistic wavefunction is linked with a potential related to the inherent force for particles with rest mass.

$\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ As Probability for Inherent Force Hits

We argue that both a particle with rest mass and a photon, which arise from special relativity, are associated with the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ which yields the same value for x,t and $x+h\bar{v}/p, t+h\bar{v}/E$. We suggest that this means that inherent force strikes (for a particle with rest mass, electric field for a photon) are linked with $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. This manifests itself physically through two slit interference patterns etc.

We note that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ has unit modulus so that $\exp(iEt-ipx)\exp(-iEt+ipx) = 1$ represents a uniform distribution with p,E and other information removed. This suggests that there exists a classical viewpoint of quantum particle density $\rho(x)=1$ and also:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

I.e., energy conservation for a single particle bound state. One may, however, ask whether ((1)) may be linked to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. If one only considers collisions in space, then one may use $\exp(ipx)$ as the interaction probability. A sum of these complex probabilities leads to an interaction in space, similar to that of 2-slit interference. If one considers $\exp(ipx)$ with a particle with rest mass, then $-i \text{grad}(-iEt+ipx) = p$ proportional to force. Thus, for a particle with rest mass, it seems that one focuses on potential. A photon, on the other hand, has an electric field proportional $\cos(-Et+px)$, but we have argued in previous notes that a photon may interact with an electric field inside an atom. In such a case, an electric field acts as a force, but not one proportional to $\cos(-Et+px)$. Rather, one has:

$$\text{Electric field} = -d/dt A - \text{grad } \phi \quad \text{where } A \text{ is the magnetic potential and } \phi, \text{ the electric } ((2))$$

Thus, quantum bound states do seem to be linked with a potential which is associated with probabilistic hits of an inherent force, but $\exp(ipx)$ is directly linked to the potential in ((1)), even for $V(x) = q \phi(x)$. As a result, we argue that quantum mechanics (at least for bound states) is a potential type problem. Thus, localization of the inherent force seems to be associated with a potential.

Completeness

Given that the Hamiltonian (energy operator) is Hermitian, one is guaranteed real eigenvalues and a complete set of eigenfunctions, so:

$$\psi(x) = \sum_n a_n \psi_n(x) \quad ((3))$$

Here $\psi_n(x)$ are eigenstates of some Hamiltonian, $V(x)$ is some potential and $\psi(x)$, some wavefunction. Given $\psi(x)$ in ((3)), one may calculate:

$$[-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d\psi}{dx}] / \psi \text{ and see if when added to } V(x) \text{ one obtains } E_n \psi(x) \quad ((4))$$

If so, then $\psi(x)$ is the n th eigenstate of $H = -\frac{1}{2m} \text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} + V(x)$. Otherwise, one may consider the expansion ((3)) which should be independent of E_n values. It is $V(x)$ acting on $\psi(x)$ which seems to create a resonance state or a sum of resonance states, and so one may consider:

$$\langle \psi_1 | V(x) | \psi_2 \rangle \propto \langle \psi_2 | V(x) | \psi_1 \rangle \text{ proportional to a transition from } \psi_2 \text{ to } \psi_1 \text{ with no } E_1, E_2 \text{ appearing} \quad ((5))$$

Given that ((5)) has units of energy squared, one may obtain units of probability per second by using:

$$1/\hbar \cdot \text{density}(E) \text{ where } \text{density}(E) \text{ has units of } 1/E \quad ((6))$$

As a result, even though the Schrodinger equation may be used to find a resonance state, we argue that by using partial information in this equation, i.e. $V(x)\psi(x)$, one may consider transitions from $\psi(x)$ to $\psi_1(x)$ in quantum mechanics. As a result, it is the interaction distribution of energy which determines transitions.

Interaction Spatial Density

Classical mechanics seems to go hand in hand with quantum interactions. For example, a free particle center-of-mass follows $x=vt$, but $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ describes the probability for an inertial mass hit. In the case of a single particle bound state:

$$K_{E_{ave}}(x) + V(x) = K_{E_{classical}}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((7))$$

Classical physics is present, but there are additional features, in particular spatial interaction patterns. This is linked to $\cos(px)$ in $\exp(ipx)$ for a time-independent problem. This pattern is important because it shows how interactions physically occur in space, but one cannot say that $\psi(x)=0$ means that there is no kinetic energy at $x=0$. For a particle in an infinite well, $\psi(x)=C\cos(p_{ave} x)$, but

$$\frac{p_{ave}}{\sqrt{2m}} \cos(p_{ave} x) / \cos(p_{ave} x) = p_{ave} \sqrt{2m} \quad ((8))$$

Classical physics is present, but $\cos(p_{ave} x)$ reveals an interaction probability distribution for m_0 (inertia) hits, we argue.

One may map the extra-informational approach $\exp(ipx)$ to the lower information approach ((7)) using ensemble averages.

This strategy can also be used to calculate Fermi's golden rule:

$$\text{Probability to transition from } W_1 \text{ to } W_2 \text{ per sec} = \frac{1}{\hbar} \langle W_2 | V(x) | W_1 \rangle \langle W_1 | V(x) | W_2 \rangle \text{density}(E) \quad ((9))$$

The approach used in (1) is a little different from the one given above, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that for the case of localized inherent forces, like m_0 (inertia) or charge (q), quantum mechanical probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (or $\exp(ipx)$ in time-independent problems) pertains to a potential energy linked with the inherent force. We also argue that classical and quantum mechanics are linked. Thus, a free particle has a center-of-mass which follows $x=vt$, but an inertia hit distribution which follows $\exp(ipx)$. For a single particle bound state, one should use classical conservation of energy to obtain an equation which maps to classical physics through the use of an ensemble average of kinetic energy. One must be sure to divide by $W(x)$ so that the probabilities are normalized: $KE_{ave}(x) = \{-1/2m d/dx dW/dx\} / W(x)$. This shows the classical type kinetic energy, but $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx$ and $V(x)W(x)$ show quantum probabilistic interactions. Thus, energy or potential calculations are critical in quantum mechanics for intrinsic forces which are localized.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fermi%27s_golden_rule